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Syntheses and Nucleophilic Additions to Conjugated Imines of 3-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole and 1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde

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AZOMETHINES are known to undergo addition reactions wherein a variety of reagents add on to the polarised double bond^{1,2}. In continuation of our earlier work, we have carried out syntheses of some imines by reacting 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole with aromatic aldehydes and reacting 1,2-dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde³ with aromatic amines. The imines 1-7 subsequently obtained gave good yields of cyanoimines (8-14) on treatment with potassium cyanide in the presence of traces of acetic acid. The imines (1-7) were also reduced to the dihydro products (15-21) with sodium borohydride.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were obtained in KBr pellets and the nmr spectrum in CDCl₃.

3-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole 4'-Nitroflavone was synthesised by the reported procedure⁴. 4'-Nitroflavone was reacted with hydroxylamine hydrochloride to yield 3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)isoxazole (A) (70%), m.p. 230°. Alternately, (A) was also obtained by reacting 4'-nitro-2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Compound (A) was then methylated by using dimethyl sulphate and refluxing with fused potassium carbonate in dry acetone to yield, 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-nitrophenyl)isoxazole (B) (60-65%), m.p. 174°.

Compound (B) was then reduced by using granulated tin and conc. hydrochloric acid to yield the amine 3-(2-methoxyphenyl)-5-(4-aminophenyl)isoxazole (50%), m.p. 137° (Found: C, 72.14; H, 5.28; N, 10.47. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₂ requires: C, 72.18; H, 5.26; N, 10.52%); ν_{max} 1 626 (C=N of isoxazole ring), 1 054 (OCH₃) and 3 500 cm⁻¹ (NH of primary amine); δ 3.69 (2H, bs, NH₂), 3.94 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9 (1H, s, C=CH of isoxazole), 6.75-7.9 (8H, m, ArH).

1,2-Dihydro-5-acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde³; A mixture of acenaphthene, *N*-methylformanilide, phosphorous oxychloride in *o*-dichlorobenzene was reacted to yield the desired aldehyde.

TABLE I

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M p. °C	Yield %	N% : Found/ (Calcd.)
1	2-Ph	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	174	85	7.49 (7.56)
2	4-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	137	60.5	10.43 (10.52)
3	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	134	70	7.18 (7.29)
4	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	91	65	7.84 (7.90)
5	4-NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	105	80	9.13 (9.27)
6	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N	98	60	5.36 (5.45)
7	4-Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ NCl	103	70	4.68 (4.80)

Imines 1-7 (Table I): (i) The isoxazole amine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol, acidified by adding a few drops of acetic acid, and then various aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The product (1-4) separated on cooling, was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. (ii) The acenaphthylenecarboxaldehyde (0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol containing a few drops of acetic acid. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The product (5-7) which separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol. The ir spectrum (KBr) showed the absorption for CH=N at 1 668 cm⁻¹.

Addition of HCN to imines 8-14 (Table 2) : The appropriate imine (1-7 ; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in methanol and the solution was made acidic by adding a few drops of acetic acid. Potassium cyanide (0.01 mol in 10 ml water) was added to the imine solution with continuous stirring at 0-5°. The product (8-14) obtained was filtered and recrystallised from methanol. 1-4 gave nitriles 8-11, whereas 5-7 yielded nitriles 12-14. The cyanoimines showed the absorption at 3 430 (NH) and 2 245 cm⁻¹ (C≡N).

TABLE 2

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p °C	Yield %	N% found/Calcd
8	2-OH	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	185	80	10.50 (10.57)
9	4-NO ₂	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	197	67	13.03 (13.14)
10	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	193	75	10.15 (10.21)
11	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	158	70	10.93 (11.02)
12	4-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	95	70	12.85 (12.77)
13	H	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ N ₂	135	60	9.75 (9.86)
14	4-Cl	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ N ₂ Cl	173	63	8.90 (8.79)

Reduction of imines 15-21 with NaBH₄ (Table 3) : Sodium borohydride (0.03 mol) was added to a methanolic solution of the imine (0.02 mol) over a period of 30 min at 5-10°. The mixture was then kept overnight at room temperature. The excess sodium borohydride was neutralised by adding water and the product extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water until neutral, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and finally evaporated. The compound (15-21) thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol. 1-4 gave the dihydro compounds (15-18), whereas 5-7 gave the dihydro compounds 19-21. The dihydro products showed the absorption at 3 300-3 250 cm⁻¹ (NH).

TABLE 3

Compd no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% : Found/Calcd
15	2-OH	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	129	55	7.44 (7.52)
16	4-NO ₂	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	209	50	10.39 (10.47)
17	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	107	56-60	7.17 (7.25)
18	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	169	45	7.79 (7.86)
19	4-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	84	60	9.16 (9.21)
20	H	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ N	115	52	5.32 (5.41)
21	4-Cl	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ NCl	165	56	4.82 (4.77)

The nitro substituted derivative showed the absorption at 1 520 cm⁻¹ which indicates that the NO₂ group does not undergo reduction during the reaction with borohydride.

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Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Hydroxyphenylethylidenebenzylamines

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A detailed survey of the literature reveals that there are only a few instances^{1,2} where imines have shown antifungal activity, and most of these imines have at least one halogen atom which